

Project Acronym:	HUTER
Project Full Name:	Human Uterus Cell Atlas
Call identifier:	H2020-SC1-2019-Single-Stage-RTD
Topic:	SC1-BHC-31-2019
Grant Agreement No:	874867
Start date of Project:	01/01/2020
Project Duration	2,5 years (30 months)
Document due date:	31/03/2022
Submission Date	04/03/2022
Leader of this report:	BAHIA
Deliverable no:	2.4
Deliverable name:	Data access and DICOM visualization tools
Dissemination level:	Open

Version History

Version	Date	Details
1.0	04/03/2022	Deliverable completed.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 874867.

The opinions expressed in this document reflect only the author's view and in no way reflect the European Commission's opinions. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

DELIVERABLE 2.4

Data access and DICOM visualization tools

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	2
List of Acronyms	5
1. PURPOSE OF THIS DOCUMENT.....	6
1.1. Related documents.....	6
2. STATUS OF DELIVERABLE.....	6
3. INTRODUCTION	7
4. FINAL DATA ACCESS TOOLS.....	7
4.1. Transversal considerations.....	9
4.1.1. Cloud infrastructure	9
4.1.2. Security.....	10
4.1.3. HUTER CLI	11
4.1.4. HUTER API.....	11
4.2. Data ingestion.....	12
4.2.1. eCRF software: LibreClinica	12
4.2.2. HUTER API – Data ingestion.....	12
4.2.3. HUTER CLI – Data Ingestion	16
4.3. Data access	18
4.3.1. HUTER API – Data Access.....	18
4.3.2. Data browser	24
4.3.3. HUTER CLI – Data Access	26

- 4.3.4. Cellxgene 27
- 4.3.5. RStudio Server 28
- 4.3.6. Data export tool..... 30
- 4.4. Processing..... 30
 - 4.4.1. Execution Manager..... 31
 - 4.4.2. Repository..... 32
 - 4.4.3. HUTER API - Processing 32
 - 4.4.4. HUTER CLI - Processing..... 33
- 4.5. Others 34
 - 4.5.1. NextCloud 34
 - 4.5.2. Private user portal 34
- 5. ADVANCED DICOM VIEWER 35
 - 5.1. Supported imaging formats..... 35
 - 5.1.1. Immunohistochemistry 36
 - 5.1.2. Tissue microarray 36
 - 5.1.3. Immunofluorescence..... 38
 - 5.1.4. smFISH 40
 - 5.2. Artificial Intelligence applied to research images 41
 - 5.2.1. Ilastik..... 42
 - 5.2.2. Segmentation/Clustering..... 43
 - 5.2.3. Cellular counting..... 46
 - 5.3. Platform integration 49
 - 5.3.1. Security 49
 - 5.3.2. PACS..... 50
 - 5.4. Architecture and technical design 50
 - 5.4.1. Component model..... 50
 - 5.4.2. Development technologies..... 51

6. REFERENCES..... 51

List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence	DAPI	4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole	scRNAseq	Single Cell RNA sequencing
API	Application Programming Interface	DICOM	Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine	SDK	Software Development Kit
AWS	Amazon Web Services	HUTER	Human Uterus Cell Atlas project	smFISH	single molecule Fluorescence In Situ Hybridization
CLI	Command Line Interface	IAM	Identity and Access Management	TMA	Tissue Microarray
D2.1	Deliverable 2.1	IDE	integrated Development Environment	tSNE	t-distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding
D2.2	Deliverable 2.2	IHC	Immunohistochemistry	UI	User Interface
D2.3	Deliverable 2.3	PACS	Picture Archiving and Communication System	UMAP	Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection
D7.1	Deliverable 7.1	PR	Presentation State	WP2	Work Package 2
D7.2	Deliverable 7.2	RNA	Ribonucleic Acid	WP7	Work Package 7

1. PURPOSE OF THIS DOCUMENT

The development of the activities regarding Deliverable D2.4 which is defined as “Final implementation of data access tools and DICOM visualization tool” has been successfully completed.

The purpose of this document is to update the previous work delivered in D2.3 (Beta version of access tools), reporting the final access tools developed and integrated in the platform from a functional perspective. The final updates, changes, improvements, and decisions made were based on the feedback provided by HUTER researchers and bioinformaticians during the project.

Collectively, this deliverable provides an overview of the work performed in terms of final tools that were developed and integrated in the HUTER platform. These tools will allow researchers to interact with data in different ways (uploading, downloading, visualization, analysis, processing and so forth) and therefore improve their workflows and facilitate their scientific tasks.

The tools and work presented herein were developed in the framework of the WP2 as part of the task 2.3, but also tightly linked to integration part of the visualization tools of task 7.2 of WP7.

1.1. Related documents

Documents linked to past actions already delivered:

HUTER_WP2_D2.1_Platform_architecture_design

HUTER_WP2_D2.2_Deployment_of_HUTER_cloud_infrastructure

HUTER_WP2_D2.3_Beta_version_of_access_tools

HUTER_WP7_D7.2_Visual_system_and_Digitalisation_software

Documents linked to future actions to be delivered:

HUTER_WP2_D2.5_DICOM_implementation

Other documents referenced:

HUTER_WP1_D1.1_Ethics_Plan

HUTER_WP9_D9.2_Data_Management_Plan

2. STATUS OF DELIVERABLE

The delivery of the final access tools and the DICOM viewer has been completed. Therefore, we consider the deliverable to be completed. However, we will continue monitoring and implementing potential improvements and refinements in these tools if needed until the project is completed.

3. INTRODUCTION

The Human Uterus Cell Atlas project (HUTER) is a molecular biology project that generates and analyses different biological data and metadata in order to achieve the cellular map of the human uterus. The HUTER platform is designed to facilitate all these tasks, decreasing the workload of the researchers with higher performance than traditional computers or servers, from any location with a computer with internet connexion. In this context, the HUTER platform requires to provide tools that interact with data in different ways, enabling the generation, processing, analysis and visualization of this data. Therefore, the HUTER platform was designed with the aim of being opened to enable the integration of any executable tool over its cloud infrastructure, accessible from any place and by any HUTER user (as explained in D2.1 and D7.1). Furthermore, the HUTER cloud infrastructure designed and deployed (D2.1, D2.2 and D7.1) allows the adaptation of resources to the computing demands of the researchers in terms of core units, speed, storage and so forth, increasing the performance of high-throughput analysis or processing and avoiding bottlenecks that could hamper or delay high-demanding tasks.

In order to detect or develop useful tools to be integrated in the platform, a wide analysis of the available open tools published by the scientific community and the identification of functionalities required in HUTER in close collaboration with HUTER bioinformaticians was reported in the context of D2.3. Then, some of the identified tools and others of own design have been developed and integrated in the platform in order to fulfil the project requirements as detailed before. This report provides an update of the D2.3 as a result of the decisions taken regarding the implementation of the final access tools (there was several options under analysis during the project), that provide access, visualization, downloading/uploading features to hosted data, and the Advanced DICOM Viewer. Since the interface of the tools were included in D7.2., this document will be focused on the rest of Data Access tools as well as the detailed explanation of the Advanced DICOM Viewer.

4. FINAL DATA ACCESS TOOLS

So far, in previous deliverables we introduced that HUTER platform provides a suite of tools and IT infrastructure for the storage and exploitation of research data. *HUTER_WP2_D2.1_Platform_architecture_design* exposes the final architecture where IT solutions are deployed in order to access the stored data for its treatment through the set of tools compiled in document *HUTER_WP2_D2.3_Beta_version_of_access_tools*. Therefore, this deliverable will be a summary of the functionalities provided by the already exposed tools and support services.

The complete list of deployed tools and services as well as their current usability status is listed in the next table:

Tool or service name	Functionality	Status
LibreClinica	Open-Source application for Electronic Case Report management.	Deployed - Active
huter-cli	Command line application for the exploitation of the HUTER Platform cloud services.	Released - Active
data-browser	Web application for browsing information in the HUTER Platform.	Deployed - Active
Cellxgene	Open Source application for omics data comparison at gene level.	Deployed - Active
RStudio Server	RStudio development tool on the cloud.	Deployed - Active
Data export tools	Ancillary tools for exporting information from HUTER Platform to the HCA DCP Platform.	Waiting for legal agreement regarding data transfer between HCA and European Commission
huter-storage-manager-files	API service for file location management and description of file characteristics like format, extension, provenance and so on.	Deployed - Active
huter-storage-manager-processes	API service for tracking any activity through the platform, for instance, file uploading or workflow executions.	Deployed - Active
huter-storage-manager-samples	API service for managing data from samples which are related to the project.	Deployed - Active
huter-storage-manager-subjects	API service for managing subject data.	Deployed – Inactive because it was not required (see explanation at 4.2.2.3 and 4.3.1.4)
huter-ingest-manager-submissions	API service for managing file storage in the HUTER platform, mainly file uploading.	Deployed - Active

huter-ingest-manager-samples	API service for running the indexation process on sample metadata files.	Deployed - Active
huter-ingest-manager-subjects	API service for running the indexation process on subject metadata files.	Developed – Not deployed because it was not required (see explanation at 4.2.2.3 and 4.3.1.4)
huter-pipeline-manager-executions	API service for managing workflows in the platform from a client application.	Deployed - Active
Nextcloud	Open-Source application for internal project managing and communication.	Deployed - Active
Private User Portal	Private area on the HUTER web for custom user access to the cloud tools.	Deployed - Active
Advanced DICOM Viewer	DICOM viewer for new proposed imaging formats in research environments and AI application.	Deployed - Active

4.1. Transversal considerations

This section is devoted to clarifying some questions that refers to all the HUTER Platform Tools. Next points have been already introduced in previous deliverables but in order to summarize their connection to all the points in the current document, they are listed again.

4.1.1. Cloud infrastructure

HUTER Platform was designed as a Cloud Platform for achieving the requirements introduced in deliverable *HUTER_WP2_D2.1_Platform_architecture_design*. For documentation coherence, it is important to remark that this deliverable will complement the data access tools explained in *HUTER_WP7_D7.2_Visual_system_and_Digitalisation_software* from a technical point of view.

Therefore, this deliverable is devoted to detailing the deployed Data Access Tools design and how they all together offer a strong environment for data exploitation in the HUTER Cloud Platform.

Figure 1 - HUTER Platform infrastructure shows the main components in the platform as well as the communication channels among them.

Figure 1 - HUTER Platform infrastructure

It is important to bear in mind that HUTER Platform has been deployed on AWS infrastructure using as main storage system the AWS S3 service. However, the platform can be easily adapted to other cloud providers such as Google Cloud or Microsoft Azure, Backblaze, Cloudflare or the European Open Science Cloud which makes it independent of a specific provider.

4.1.2. Security

Regarding deliverable *HUTER_WP9_D9.2_Data_Management_Plan*, HUTER Platform has to be compliant with the introduced ethic rules and data security assurance. The compliant security components were introduced in document *HUTER_WP2_D2.1_Platform_architecture_design*. So, to sum up we will remind that any access to the platform is verified through a OAuth2 system provided by a Keycloak Server, which works as a Single Sign On, and the AWS IAM service. Hence, all the next tools in this document are integrated with the HUTER Security system although they run in a non-cloud device like HUTER CLI.

4.1.3. HUTER CLI

HUTER CLI (or `huter-cli`) is a command line tool devoted to communicating user devices with the HUTER Platform services. Document *HUTER_WP7_D7.2_Visual_system_and_Digitalisation_software* showed the user interface so in this deliverable, some additional details will be explained.

The first issue to be treated is that HUTER CLI is a client application, this means that no data processing is done on the machine where HUTER CLI is running. Therefore, this tool just requests the execution of cloud services which works with the data in the platform. However, not all the functionalities can be done on the cloud, for instance, the effort of uploading a file is mainly done by the HUTER CLI what it is obvious because files are in the local device.

In *Figure 2 - huter-cli component design* the structure of the HUTER CLI is shown. The diagram express how HUTER CLI is a tool that coordinates the communication with platform services instead of processing data by itself.

Figure 2 - *huter-cli component design*

This tool was developed using Spring Boot 2 over Java 8. Furthermore, it integrates the Keycloak client and the AWS SDK for cloud storage access as well as HUTER API clients. So, technical requirements for running this tool are quite simple because only a Java 8 Runtime Environment has to be provided.

Additionally, this application was designed to run on common S.O. like Windows, Linux and Mac.

4.1.4. HUTER API

HUTER API is a set of services devoted to managing the access to the information in the platform. The complete set of deployed services is shown in *4 FINAL DATA ACCESS TOOLS* but not all of them are involved in the data ingestion.

HUTER API was designed following the API REST approach and when it was feasible, RESTful operations. The development stack was composed of Java 11, Spring Boot 2 and MongoDB access through Mongo Template. Some services also required the integration of the AWS SDK and additional REST client for GITEA and Cromwell.

4.2. Data ingestion

Data gathering functionalities are assembled to point out the interaction with subject and sample data collection. Therefore, the HUTER platform provides data registration tools to safely collect, validate and store information in the system.

4.2.1. eCRF software: LibreClinica

LibreClinica is a fork of OpenClinica, an open-source software initially designed for clinical trial studies but now adapted to the HUTER project requirements by BAHIA. This component allows to manage electronic case report forms (eCRFs) by a web interface that gathers the questionnaire information as it was shown in deliverables *HUTER_WP2_D2.3_Beta_version_of_access_tools* and *HUTER_WP7_D7.2_Visual_system_and_Digitalisation_software*.

Previous deliverables have detailed the final version of LibreClinica deployment, so no additional information will be added about it in this section far from its runtime requirements. So, for running LibreClinica the required environment is JDK11, Tomcat 9 and PosgreSQL 11.

Further information can be checked at <https://www.libreclinica.org>.

4.2.2. HUTER API – Data ingestion

There is a subset of services in the 4.1.4 HUTER API that are specifically devoted to receiving data uploading requests from different sources. This subset is shown in *Figure 3 - Ingest manager subset of services* as *Ingest Manager* and it contains the next services.

Figure 3 - Ingest manager subset of services

4.2.2.1. *huter-ingest-manager-submissions*

This service is responsible for receiving uploading requests for new files. For each request, it registers an uploading process and provisions the location of the files in the cloud storage avoiding file name collisions. Furthermore, the storage provision assures the folder organization sent by the user. For doing that, *huter-ingest-manager-submissions* service exposes an API REST that can be seen at *Figure 4 - huter-ingest-manager-submissions service operations*.

It is also responsible for verifying those files are properly stored when the uploading process is finished as well as update the registry in the HUTER central database. Once this has been done, the files are available for their use in the platform tools and services.

For data registration in the HUTER database, this service is integrated with other services in the HUTER API that are devoted to managing file and process data. These services are *huter-storage-manager-files* and *huter-storage-manager-processes* that will be explained in the section *4.3 Data access*.

Figure 4 - *huter-ingest-manager-submissions* service operations

4.2.2.2. *huter-ingest-manager-samples*

The indexation of sample metadata in the HUTER database is a complementary process that allow users to link uploaded files to experimental data from samples. Once the sample metadata is on the database, users can locate the files containing the information related to a set of samples simply selecting sample features.

For indexing sample metadata, users must firstly upload a set of TSV files containing all the sample information, including the sample identifiers. The main reason for uploading these files is not their data indexation but to be assigned to workflow executions as input parameters. That is because the TSV format is more accessible for analytic software than retrieving data from a database to a bioinformatician analysis pipeline. Taking advantage of this situation, the indexation process can be run in a cloud service over the ingested sample metadata files to complement the HUTER Platform functionalities.

Allowed users can request the indexation of sample metadata through the HUTER CLI. This tool communicates to the *huter-ingest-manager-samples* using the REST API.

The data indexation process requires some parameters that were described in *HUTER_WP7_D7.2_Visual_system_and_Digitalisation_software* and they are:

- a list of metadata files previously stored in the platform
- a file for configuring the indexation process.

The first parameter is a manifest file, that can be generated through the *Data browser*, which contains a list of files within sample metadata. The files must be stored in the platform, that is why manifest file should be generated through the *Data browser*. Furthermore, the current format for sample metadata files should be plain TSV files where each column is related to a sample feature and each row a different sample.

The second parameter is a file called ingestion-schema, see *Figure 5 - Ingest-schema example*, and works as a mapping guide between each column in the sample metadata file and the database. At least one row must exist in this file to point out the column in the sample metadata file that contains the sample identifier. The rest of the columns, if absent or not configured as fields of the fixed sample structure in the HUTER Platform, will be ingested as dynamic features of the sample in the database.

The structure of the ingest-schema is quite straight-forward. Using a TSV format there are six columns for configuring the mapping over a column of a sample metadata file. The first row of the file is a tile guide because users can modify this mapping to fit their needs.

- Column: user can provide the name of a column that exists in the sample metadata file. At least the column containing the sample identifier has to be added.

- Excluded: users can indicate not to index in the database the named column. For instance, the Project_code column in the sample metadata file will not be indexed because is configured as “excluded=yes”.
- huter-field: it must contain a pre-set value for mapping the column in the sample metadata file to a specific field of the sample registry defined in the HUTER Platform.
- Category: it is a field that allows users to assign a category to a dynamic feature for avoiding collision when sample metadata is provided from several institutions.
- healing-value-protocol: even when values are expected to be index as they are, some treatment is required for usability reasons. For instance, in order to properly managing dates, they must firstly be translated from a specific form to a common one, therefore, no information is altered but format.
- healing-title-value: some sample metadata is related to their source subject. That information is gathered in the *eCRF software: LibreClinica* and then exported to a TSV file for its exploitation. HUTER bioinformaticians have included a subset of the exported subject data in the sample metadata file using the LibreClinica format. Unfortunately, LibreClinica add some internal identifiers to the exported column names, so we suggested to clean up the titles by erasing the LibreClinica identifiers.

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	column	excluded	huter-field	category	healing-value-protocol	healing-title-protocol
2	Cell_suspension_ID		huter-sample-code			
3	Obt-Date		obtainmentDate		DATE_dd-MM-yy	
4	Project_name		study			
5	Project_code	yes				
6	Navision_Code		incliva-sample-code/uea-sample-code			
7	Country		site			
8	CollectionSite		institution			
9	Study_Subject_ID		huter-subject-code		HUTER-SUBJECT-CODE	
10	Female_age_years_E6_C6_					LIBRECLINICA
11	Height_value_E6_C6_					LIBRECLINICA
12	Weight_value_E6_C6_					LIBRECLINICA
13	Female_BMI_value_E6_C6_					LIBRECLINICA
14	Age_Offset_Calculation_E6_C6_	yes				LIBRECLINICA
15	Weight_E6_C6_			uea		LIBRECLINICA
16	Ethnicity_E6_C6_					LIBRECLINICA
17	Height_E6_C6_					LIBRECLINICA
18	BMI_range_E6_C6_					LIBRECLINICA
19	Menstrual_cycle_E6_C6_					LIBRECLINICA
20	Menstrual_Period_E6_C6_			incliva		LIBRECLINICA
21	Anticonceptives_or_IUD_E6_C6_					LIBRECLINICA
22	Menstrual_cycle_day_sampling_E6_C6_					LIBRECLINICA
23	Current_menstrual_formula_E6_C6_					LIBRECLINICA
24	Last_menstrual_period_sampling_DATE_E6_C6_					LIBRECLINICA
25	Sampling_DATE_E6_C6_				DATE_dd-MM-yyyy	LIBRECLINICA
26	Menstrual_period_after_sampling_DATE_E6_C6_					LIBRECLINICA
27	Female_age_E6_C6_	yes				LIBRECLINICA
28	Negative_serological_tests_E6_C6_					LIBRECLINICA
29	Normal_Karyotype_E6_C6_					LIBRECLINICA
30	Regular_menstrual_formula_E6_C6_					LIBRECLINICA
31	Female_BMI_E6_C6_	yes				LIBRECLINICA
32	Previous_pregnancy_sPE_E6_C6_					LIBRECLINICA
33	Previous_pregnancy_complication_EN_E6_C6_					LIBRECLINICA
34	Previous_pregnancy_E6_C6_					LIBRECLINICA
35	Previous_pregnancy_with_complications_E6_C6_					LIBRECLINICA
36	Previous_live_birth_number_E6_C6_					LIBRECLINICA
37	Previous_miscariages_E6_C6_					LIBRECLINICA
38	Number_all_previous_gestations_E6_C6_					LIBRECLINICA
39						
40						

Figure 5 - Ingest-schema example

Regarding to the sample registry management, the sample ingestion service does not access directly to the database but it is integrated with the *huter-storage-manager-samples* service that will be explained in section 4.3 *Data access*. Using the HUTER API, the sample registry management, like searching, updating, creation and so on, is delegated into the *huter-storage-manager-samples* service.

The data indexation process is obvious according to the previously named parameters. A summary of its steps is listed next.

1. *huter-ingest-manager-samples* service check the ingestion-schema in order to load the mapping rules between the sample metadata file and the sample registry in the database.
2. *huter-ingest-manager-samples* service receives the manifest files containing the location of the sample metadata files. Then, it downloads these files from the cloud storage to a local one for their processing one by one.
3. The ingestion process treats each row of the files in order to create or update and existing sample registry. So, for the current sample row, the mapping process described in the ingest-schema is applied in order to create a sample registry that will be created or updated, if it already exists.

4.2.2.3. *huter-ingest-manager-subjects*

This service was designed for indexing data of the subjects involved in the HUTER assays. The suggested approach was the same implemented for the *huter-ingest-manager-samples* service, however, after deep conversations with the HUTER project bioinformaticians we solve not to deploy this service because the subject metadata will be manually included and checked within the sample metadata. Besides, this method also assures that each sample had it subject metadata regarding to the extraction date, what avoids the need of subject metadata managing.

4.2.3. HUTER CLI – Data Ingestion

The HUTER CLI tool was developed to provide a comfortable and easy-to-use interface for HUTER platform exploitation. Deliverable *HUTER_WP7_D7.2_Visual_system_and_Digitalisation_software* showed how users can run HUTER Platform functionalities but now, we will explain how it works under the hood regarding data ingestion processes.

4.2.3.1. *File uploading*

HUTER CLI allows users to upload files to a cloud storage for a later exploitation through the HUTER Platform tools. Document *HUTER_WP7_D7.2_Visual_system_and_Digitalisation_software* exposed how users can perform file uploads using this command line and the parameters they must provide. Considering that the uploading process is separated in two steps, next section will argue about each one and their benefits.

The first step is the arrangement of the file upload from a local folder. *Figure 6 - huter-cli prepare* shows the HUTER CLI command that allow users to provision the needed resources by invoking the *huter-ingest-manager-submissions* service. Additional parameters are used by the service to register files in the HUTER Platform while adding some useful file metadata like file information category, a summary of the file information and, optionally, identifiers of the related subject and sample.

```

C:\Windows\System32\cmd.exe
D:\desenrol\huter\data-access-tools\huter-cli>java -jar huter-cli-dev-v.01.03.jar prepare -h
huter-cli - 01.03.0000-SNAPSHOT - dev - Loading prepare...
huter-cli - 01.03.0000-SNAPSHOT - dev - Running requested execution.
huter-cli - 01.03.0000-SNAPSHOT - dev -

This command executes the previous step for file uploading to the platform. The outcome will be an early file registration in the platform index. Files will be
stored keeping the input folder structure. Additional data have be provided in order to support basic browsing features.

Available prepare options
-----
-d <mandatory> Local working directory where files are located. If subfolders exist, the current structure will remain in the platform storage under a calculat
ed remote folder.
-t <mandatory> Code describing file type. Allowed values are ANALYSIS, IMAGE, REFERENCE, SCRNA_SEQUENCE, WHOLEGENOME_SEQUENCE, SC METHYL_SEQUENCE,
SUPPLEMENTARY, SUBJECT_METADATA, SAMPLE_METADATA. Value provided in this option will be added to all files in the directory that will be
prepared for ingestion. Valid File types are:
  - ANALYSIS: files generated from a transformation process.
  - IMAGE: imaging files, regardless of the format.
  - REFERENCE: files with master data or known data models.
  - SCRNA_SEQUENCE: Single Cell RNA Sequencing data files.
  - WHOLEGENOME_SEQUENCE: Whole Genome Sequencing data files.
  - SUPPLEMENTARY: files with additional data that are not associated with other categories.
  - SUBJECT_METADATA: files containing data of study subjects exported from the CRP.
  - SAMPLE_METADATA: files that contain sample data and that can be indexed on the platform.
  - SC METHYL_SEQUENCE: Single Cell DNA Methylation Sequencing data Files.
-c <mandatory> Custom code provided by the uploader in order to identify this execution: run on scrnaseq, TMA code, container code for other samples, etc. It wi
ll also be assigned to the process name for searching purposes.
-m <mandatory> Custom description to be assigned to the upload process and files.
--subject <optional> Registration code of the subject that files refer to. It can only be refered to the project code catalog.
--sample <optional> Registration code of the sample that files refer to. It can only be refered to the project code catalog.
-h
  It shows this help.

huter-cli - 01.03.0000-SNAPSHOT - dev - The operation was successfully executed. You can check the details of the prepared files in the submission.json file locat
ed on the following route: D:\desenrol\huter\data-access-tools\huter-cli
D:\desenrol\huter\data-access-tools\huter-cli>
  
```

Figure 6 - huter-cli prepare

After the “prepare” step, files are registered in PROVISIONED status so they can be checked through the 4.3.2 *Data browser*. However, files are not uploaded yet because a second step for data transferring is needed. Users can perform this action over a previously “prepared” folder by running the *Figure 7 - huter-cli ingestfiles* command.

```

C:\Windows\System32\cmd.exe
D:\desenrol\huter\data-access-tools\huter-cli>java -jar huter-access-cli-01.02.0001-RELEASE.jar ingestfiles -h
huter-cli - 01.02.0001-RELEASE - dev - Loading ingestfiles...
huter-cli - 01.02.0001-RELEASE - dev - Running requested execution.
huter-cli - 01.02.0001-RELEASE - dev -

This command starts syncing files from local environment to the cloud storage. It involves uploading
and removing from the bucket all files that are not registered in the submission.json.

Available ingestfiles options
-----
-d
  Required. Directory in which files and folders to be uploaded will be searched.
-m
  Optional. If this options is added, upload will be perform in multipart mode if possible.
-h
  It shows this help

huter-cli - 01.02.0001-RELEASE - dev -
D:\desenrol\huter\data-access-tools\huter-cli>
  
```

Figure 7 - huter-cli ingestfiles

HUTER CLI file ingestion functionality uploads files to the cloud storage using the location assigned by the *huter-ingest-manager-submissions* service in the “prepare” step invocation. Once all files are uploaded, HUTER CLI sends a request to the *huter-ingest-manager-submissions* service for checking files in the cloud space.

Whether no inconsistency is found, file registries are updated as correct files what allows their exploitation using the HUTER Data Access Tools.

4.2.3.2. Metadata indexation

This section will only talk about sample metadata indexation because the equivalent process for subject metadata was not deployed and tested. However, both processes would be performed in the same way from the HUTER CLI because this tool just works as a request sender to the 4.2.2.2 *huter-ingest-manager-samples*.

User provides the manifest files containing the location of the desired sample metadata files and the ingest-schema through the command-line interface shown in *Figure 8 - huter-cli ingestsamples*. HUTER CLI just communicates this data to the 4.2.2.2 *huter-ingest-manager-samples* using a REST request.


```
C:\Windows\System32\cmd.exe
D:\desenrolo\huter\data-access-tools\huter-cli>java -jar huter-cli-dev-u.01.03.jar ingestsamples -h
huter-cli - 01.03.0000-SNAPSHOT - dev - Loading ingestsamples...
huter-cli - 01.03.0000-SNAPSHOT - dev - Running requested execution...
huter-cli - 01.03.0000-SNAPSHOT - dev -

This command starts syncing samples from local environment to the cloud storage. It involves all samples included in the manifest
file provided in the -m option

Available ingestsamples options
-----
-m (mandatory) Manifest file path in which samples that will be updated are present. In this manifest, the references to SAMPLE_METADATA files pr
eviously ingested
that will be used to ingest sample metadata information in the platform must be included

-s (mandatory) Schema file path that includes the schema of the samples that will be ingested in the platform

-h It shows this help.

huter-cli - 01.03.0000-SNAPSHOT - dev - The operation was successfully executed
D:\desenrolo\huter\data-access-tools\huter-cli>
```

Figure 8 - huter-cli ingestsamples

4.3. Data access

This section gathers the deployed tools and services that allow user to exploit the stored information in the HUTER Platform.

Some components allow users to manage the raw data, others offer metadata managing and, finally, other ones interpret raw data for human visualization.

4.3.1. HUTER API – Data Access

HUTER API has some services devoted to managing the metadata of the stored information. In this context, metadata refers to those characteristics that describes the entity, but it is not the raw data. For instance, an image file can contain a graphical description of a sample, but the file metadata is related to the image format, its size, resolution and so forth.

So, HUTER API uses a microservices approach to expose next services in order to manage different kind of entities and their metadata. The target of this set of services is not only to provide a façade for accessing to the HUTER database but also concealing some additional verifications and protocols over the data from a unique and reusable service.

All services in the HUTER API follows the REST approach for simple and universal access from many technologies and platforms.

4.3.1.1. *huter-storage-manager-files*

This service is devoted to managing file metadata. Perhaps, it is the most important service because it works as an index of the cloud storage that allows clients to manage any file in the platform.

This service is consumed by other services and applications in the platform like *huter-ingest-manager-submissions* or the *Data browser*, for creating or browsing file information.

The set of operations that can be executed is shown in *Figure 9 - huter-storage-manager-files operations*.

Swagger
storage-manager-files/api-docs Explore

Storage Manager Files API ^{4.1} OAS3

storage-manager-files/api-docs

Servers
http://localhost:8082/storage-manager-files - Generated server url Authorize

file-resource

- GET /v1/files/{uuid} Get a file through a given UUID
- PUT /v1/files/{uuid} Updates a file by its uuid
- DELETE /v1/files/{uuid} Deletes a file through a given UUID
- PATCH /v1/files/{uuid} Patches a file
- GET /v1/files Retrieves a list of paginated and filtered files
- PUT /v1/files Updates a list of files
- POST /v1/files Registers a list of files
- DELETE /v1/files Deletes a list of files
- POST /v1/files/manifest Register a FileManifest within lines each one representing a file
- POST /v1/files/find Retrieves a list of paginated and filtered files receiving a filter in the request body
- GET /v1/files/metadata Retrieves a list of paginated searchableFieldMetadata

Schemas

- Code >
- FileCore >
- FileRequest >
- Integrity >
- Process >
- Provenance >
- Sample >
- Subject >
- FileResponse >
- Links >
- PageMetadata >
- PagedModelFileResponse >
- Pageable >
- BodyFileFilter >
- JsonPatch >
- EntityModelSearchableFieldMetadata >
- FieldType >
- PagedModelEntityModelSearchableFieldMetadata >
- Restriction >
- UriFileFilter >
- Link >

Figure 9 - huter-storage-manager-files operations

4.3.1.2. *huter-storage-manager-processes*

This service is devoted to managing any process information in the platform. A process is expected to be any action executed in the platform that can generate new information, mainly, as new files. Furthermore, processes are used to keep tracking the file processing and the related metadata by saving the input and output files of each process. Therefore, HUTER Platform can keep tracking of the source samples that ends up into a results file. For instance, file uploading is a process that can be tracked for knowing who, when and which files were uploaded to the HUTER Platform.

The set of operations that can be executed is shown in *Figure 10 - huter-storage-manager-processes operations*.

The screenshot displays the Swagger UI for the 'Storage Manager Processes API'. At the top, there's a navigation bar with the Swagger logo and the API name. Below that, a 'Servers' section shows the current server URL and an 'Authorize' button. The main content is divided into two sections: 'process-resource' and 'Schemas'. The 'process-resource' section lists several endpoints with their respective HTTP methods and descriptions. The 'Schemas' section lists various data models used in the API.

Method	Endpoint	Description
GET	/v1/processes/{uuid}	Get a process by a given UUID
PUT	/v1/processes/{uuid}	Updates a process
DELETE	/v1/processes/{uuid}	Deletes a process through a given UUID
PATCH	/v1/processes/{uuid}	Patches a process
GET	/v1/processes	Retrieves a list of paginated and filtered processes
PUT	/v1/processes	Updates a list of processes
POST	/v1/processes	It registers a the processes in the request.
DELETE	/v1/processes	Deletes a list of processes
POST	/v1/processes/find	Retrieves a list of paginated and filtered processes
GET	/v1/processes/metadata	Retrieves a list of paginated searchableFieldMetadata

Schemas

- Code >
- FileStorage >
- ProcessRequest >
- Sample >
- Subject >
- Links >
- ProcessResponse >
- Status >
- Pageable >
- BodyProcessFilter >
- EntityModelProcessResponse >
- PageMetadata >
- PagedModelEntityModelProcessResponse >
- JsonPatch >
- EntityModelSearchableFieldMetadata >
- FieldType >
- PagedModelEntityModelSearchableFieldMetadata >
- Restriction >
- UriProcessFilter >
- Link >

Figure 10 - huter-storage-manager-processes operations

4.3.1.3. *huter-storage-manager-samples*

This service is devoted to managing sample metadata. Like the *huter-storage-manager-files* service, this one allows HUTER Platform tools and services to access to sample metadata for building complex processes. It is also used for offering additional features like file browsing from sample metadata from the *Data browser* what takes advantage of the *4.2.3.2 Metadata indexation*.

The set of operations that can be executed is shown in Figure 11 - *huter-storage-manager-samples* operations.

The screenshot displays the Swagger UI for the 'Storage Manager Samples API v1 OAS3'. At the top, there is a search bar with the text 'storage-manager-samples/api-docs' and an 'Explore' button. Below the search bar, the API title 'Storage Manager Samples API v1 OAS3' is shown. A 'Servers' section contains a dropdown menu with the URL 'http://localhost:8082/storage-manager-samples - Generated server url' and an 'Authorize' button. The main content is divided into two sections: 'sample-resource' and 'Schemas'. The 'sample-resource' section lists several endpoints with their methods, paths, and descriptions:

- GET** /v1/samples/{uuid} Get a sample through a given UUID
- PUT** /v1/samples/{uuid} Updates a sample by its uuid
- DELETE** /v1/samples/{uuid} Deletes a sample through a given UUID
- GET** /v1/samples Retrieves a list of paginated and filtered samples
- PUT** /v1/samples Updates a list of samples
- POST** /v1/samples Registers a Sample
- GET** /v1/samples/metadata Retrieves a list of paginated searchableFieldMetadata

The 'Schemas' section contains a list of expandable items, each with a right-pointing arrow:

- Code
- Feature
- Provenance
- Reference
- SampleCore
- SampleRequest
- Links
- SampleResponse
- PageMetadata
- PagedModelSampleResponse
- Pageable
- FieldType
- PagedModelSearchableFieldMetadata
- Restriction
- SearchableFieldMetadata
- UriSampleFilter
- Link

Figure 11 - *huter-storage-manager-samples* operations

4.3.1.4. *huter-storage-manager-subjects*

This service was designed to managing subject metadata. Its approach was like the 4.3.1.3 *huter-storage-manager-samples* but for accessing subject data. It was also expected to be used for offering file browsing from subject metadata from the *Data browser* taking advantage of the 4.2.3.2 Metadata indexation. However, because data related to subject is included in the sample metadata it can be exploited from the *huter-storage-manager-samples* service. This service was designed but eventually inactive what it is coherent with section *huter-ingest-manager-subjects* where we explain that subject metadata ingestion was not deployed.

4.3.2. Data browser

Data Browser is the friendliest user interface for managing the HUTER Platform. It was designed as a web application using a modern web framework for offering a good user experience while accessing the data on the platform. The application is composed of two pieces, a front-end application built with Vue.JS 3 and a backend developed using Java 11 and Spring Boot 2 following an API REST approach. The access to the Data Browser is controlled by applying the measures described in section 4.1.2 *Security* by integrating the OAuth2 protocol.

Deliverable *HUTER_WP7_D7.2_Visual_system_and_Digitalisation_software* exposes the functionalities of the Data Browser so next sections will address additional features previously introduced.

4.3.2.1. File functionalities

Data browser allows users to find stored files in the platform as well as execute some additional functionalities related to them.

Figure 12 - Data browser - File Search shows the interface for file search and for loading complementary tools.

Figure 12 - Data browser - File Search

File search functionality is executed by integrating the Data Browser front-end application to the backend using REST requests. Of course, these request are made over HTTPS and the backend is only available through a previous authentication against a OAuth2 service.

For enclosing the search of files, Data browser provides to the users some widgets for selecting filters on file metadata, shown in Figure 13 - Data browser - File filters, and sample metadata. These filtering options are built dynamically, which means that Data Browser can create filters over new fields and exploit them just by configuring them in the corresponding service of the *HUTER API – Data Access*.

Figure 13 - Data browser - File filters

4.3.2.2. Process functionalities

The interface for process search in the Data browser is simply enough to not require further information. Figure 14 - Data Browser - Process Search shows how the interface let users to search for any process executed in the platform, even failed ones.

HUTER Code T1	Additional Code T1	Name T1	Description T1	Type T1	Institution T1	Creation User T1	Creation Date T1	Status T1
> INGEST000001 (huter-process-code)	BH0001 (huter-lab-code)	BH0001	Test upload 20210705	INGEST	Bahia	antonio.martinez	5/7/2021 20:59:37	OK
> INGEST000002 (huter-process-code)	test001 (huter-lab-code)	test001	test.fastq	INGEST	UEA	claudia.buhigas	4/8/2021 12:46:12	PROVISIONED
> INGEST0000003 (huter-process-code)	20211001001 (huter-lab-code)	20211001001	Subida prueba a DEV 2021-10-01 001	INGEST	Bahia	test-creator	1/10/2021 19:58:27	OK
> INGEST0000004 (huter-process-code)	20211007001 (huter-lab-code)	20211007001	Subida prueba 2021-10-07 001	INGEST	Bahia	test-creator	7/10/2021 15:49:50	PROVISIONED
> INGEST0000005 (huter-process-code)	20211018004 (huter-lab-code)	20211018004	Subida prueba 2021-10-18 004	INGEST	Bahia	test-creator	18/10/2021 21:04:55	DELETED
> INGEST0000006 (huter-process-code)	20211018004 (huter-lab-code)	20211018004	Subida prueba 2021-10-18 004	INGEST	Bahia	test-creator	18/10/2021 21:05:26	DELETED
> INGEST0000007 (huter-process-code)	20211019001 (huter-lab-code)	20211019001	Subida prueba 2021-10-19 001	INGEST	Bahia	test-creator	19/10/2021 12:31:33	OK
> INGEST0000008 (huter-process-code)	20211019003 (huter-lab-code)	20211019003	Subida prueba 2021-10-19 003	INGEST	Bahia	test-creator	19/10/2021 14:21:46	PROVISIONED
> INGEST0000009 (huter-process-code)	20211019004 (huter-lab-code)	20211019004	Subida prueba 2021-10-19 004	INGEST	Bahia	test-creator	19/10/2021 14:26:47	OK
> INGEST0000014 (huter-process-code)	21/10/2021002 (huter-lab-code)	21/10/2021002	Subida prueba 21/10/2021 002	INGEST	Bahia	test-creator	21/10/2021 14:09:06	OK

Figure 14 - Data Browser - Process Search

This functionality complements the HUTER CLI because users can check their actions performed from the command line using a more agile interface.

4.3.3. HUTER CLI – Data Access

HUTER CLI was designed as the very first tool for the HUTER Platform for managing raw data. This means that users will not visualize or transform file information using the HUTER CLI but they will need the HUTER CLI to request the execution of the cloud services over the stored files.

However, for boosting the collaboration among partners in the HUTER project and for easing the platform adoption, we decided to offer the chance of downloading files from the platform.

4.3.3.1. File downloading

Even when *Data browser* could be expected as most suitable tool for offering this functionality, some technical issues could make it an unstable solution. That was one of the reasons for integrating the download option from the HUTER CLI. The other one was the approach of turning HUTER CLI into the complete solution for HUTER Platform management instead of dispersing functionalities among several tools.

This approach does not stop from integrating those functionalities in other HUTER Platform tools for a better user experience working on the platform.

Regarding to the file download feature, Deliverable *HUTER_WP7_D7.2_Visual_system_and_Digitalisation_software* introduced all the required details because this is one of the functionalities that does not mandatory require the communication to the *HUTER API – Data Access*.

4.3.4. Cellxgene

The HUTER project and other HCA projects generate scRNAseq datasets with millions of cells. Due to the high dimensionality, it is not always feasible to visualize scRNAseq data and share it in a scientific report or an article publication format. Some interactive tools are being developed to address this issue and facilitate knowledge transfer in the scientific community and decrease the cognitive workload of researchers that deal with these types of datasets. In this context, after a wide analysis with HUTER bioinformaticians and researchers, [cellxgene](#) was the available open tool finally selected to be integrated within the HUTER platform, which is compatible with .h5ad dataset files. Thanks to the integration of this tool in the HUTER platform, users can find and launch a scRNAseq dataset in .h5ad format directly from the Data browser of the HUTER platform shown in *Figure 15 – Launching cellxgene from HUTER data browser.*

Figure 15 – Launching cellxgene from HUTER data browser

Cellxgene's user interface organizes single cell data similarly to how it is organized in single cell data formats. The left-hand side displays categorical and numerical sample metadata. The right-hand side is a space for displaying features such as genes and gene sets. The center displays the embedding, where each cell is a point. UMAP and tSNE are common embeddings, which place cells based on their local distances in gene expression space. Cells from spatial data can also be displayed using each cell's (x, y) coordinates shown in *Figure 16 - Cellxgene – User interface.*

Figure 16 - Cellxgene – User interface

Among their main functionalities, we would like to highlight the following ones:

- **Cell selection tool:** the users would require performing analyses and comparisons of group of cells. Therefore, it requires to select cell populations of interest. Cellxgene allows the user to select the cells by drawing a free shape curve around the cells of interest.
- **Zoom functionality:** the ability to zoom in and out can be crucial to visually analyse and validate the data. Additionally, cellxgene also provides to switch between multiple embeddings (e.g. tSNE and UMAP), which helps with the analysis.
- **Highlight by values:** cellxgene allows to highlight either gene expression levels or cell metadata, which are two of the most important features of this kind of tool.
- **Other analysis features:** cellxgene also allows to perform differential expression analysis between different cell groups, cell-type annotation and marker gene identification.

Further information regarding features and tutorials of Cellxgene can be obtained at <https://github.com/chanzuckerberg/cellxgene-documentation/blob/main/README.md>

4.3.5. RStudio Server

The integration of the Open-Source version of the R Studio Server is a successful effort for providing a complete platform where bioinformaticians may perform their daily work on a cloud platform.

Researchers and bioinformaticians requires to perform explorative analysis and statistical comparisons between different groups or biological parameters, such as differential expression, in order to discover new

insights. For that, they require to defend their hypothesis using statistical analyses. In this context, the most widely extended statistical language among biomedical researchers is R.

For this reason, the HUTER platform integrates the RStudio server. It provides an integrated development environment (IDE) for this language. It includes a console, syntax-highlighting editor that supports direct code execution, as well as tools for plotting, history, debugging and workspace management *Figure 17 – Rstudio Server – User interface*. As a programming language, the possibilities of this tool are almost infinite in terms of analysis capabilities. This software is usually used by bioinformaticians in their computers or servers to perform any analysis using R language in an easy way.

Figure 17 – Rstudio Server – User interface

Although the functionalities of the RStudio Server have already been included in *deliverable D7.2*, is important to highlight that the integration of the RStudio Server enables the ingestion of any result, plot, files and so forth generated by the R Studio server in the HUTER platform storage. Because most of the R analysis that the researchers have to perform in their daily work are exploratory, most of them are not necessary to be stored. These includes exploratory analysis, proof of concepts, proof of scripts and so forth. However, when researchers are obtaining final data analyses, it is crucial to store this data within the HUTER platform. In that context, the integration performed with the HUTER CLI tool address this requirement, as explained in *deliverable D7.2*.

Obviously, RStudio server requires that the user knows R language in order to perform analyses. Further information about RStudio Server can be obtained at <https://www.rstudio.com/products/rstudio/#rstudio-server>.

4.3.6. Data export tool

This tool was expected to help during the transferring of the stored metadata in the HUTER Platform to the HCA DCP platform. In this context, we have held several meetings with HCA staff and HCA Data Wrangler Team regarding the data transference. However, some legal aspects regarding data transfer between HCA and the European Commission have to be overcome before sharing any data between platforms. Therefore, no technical progress has been done related to this task.

4.4. Processing

The HUTER Platform provides a solution for high throughput data processing. This functionality chases the capacity of building and executing any kind of process over the stored data as well as saving the outcomes in the platform. Therefore, this solution offers a complete data life cycle that allows users to manage all the data inside the platform.

The very first requirement that causes the deployment of this service was the need of executing bioinformatician analysis workflows over the stored omics data. Furthermore, omics data is presented as large files what demands lot of machine resources for its treatment.

An additional requirement was the need of letting bioinformaticians to decide the software and runtime for their analysis processes. This means that the processing service should support a wide set of environments like python, java or R runtimes for custom software execution. Once this requirement is covered, the processing solution cannot be only used to perform analysis over omics data but also to execute any kind of software over the files in the platform. For instance, BAHIA uses it for executing the transformation of the images from digital microscopies into ones in DICOM format, including their store in a PACS solution.

For addressing all the requirements, BAHIA designed a flexible solution based on the components shown in *Figure 18 - Solution for Data processing* with the next main responsibilities:

- Repository: it is a set of storage applications for saving the code of the bioinformaticians workflows and runtime definitions.
- Scalable backend: it is a deployment infrastructure for provision and running parallel runtime environments for the workflows.
- Pipeline Manager: it is an application for managing execution requests on a backend that will be explained in section 4.4.1 *Execution Manager*.
- Pipeline Manager Executions: it is a service of the HUTER API devoted to orchestrating the execution according to the HUTER Platform approach. Section 4.4.3 *HUTER API - Processing* will go in depth with this service and its functionality.

Figure 18 - Solution for Data processing

4.4.1. Execution Manager

The HUTER Platform solution for high performance processing requires an application for managing the execution requests. This application is responsible for receiving executions requests and organize their executions on a backend.

This means that it communicates to the backend for provisioning the runtime environment previously defined in the repository and executing the workflow on it. Besides, it performs the input parameters arrangement to the runtime as well as managing the outcomes of the process, like moving the resulting files to the storage space.

The management of execution tasks on a backend requires dealing with some issues like the machine provision, the S.O. configuration, dependency provision, infrastructure integration and so on. This kind of development is not affordable in a short-term project like HUTER Project so that is why, instead of building a custom application, BAHIA has deployed a recognized solution called Cromwell.

4.4.1.1. Cromwell

Cromwell is a Workflow Management System build by the [Broad Institute](#) as Open-source software. This system is focus on supporting the execution of scientific software that requires many resources. However, the Broad Institute solution is so adaptable that it can run almost any kind of software.

The decision for deploying Cromwell as execution manager is supported by several reasons:

- It is a stable system developed by a celebrated institution.
- It is a system focus on scientific environments so many issues related to research environments are expected to be solved.
- Its architecture fits the HUTER Platform requirements regarding infrastructure and integration with the deployment platform.

- It provides components for performing reliable communications to main cloud deployment platforms such as Amazon AWS, Google Cloud or Azure.

Apart from IT solutions, Cromwell also provides scripting languages for building the workflows to be run: WDL and CWL. These languages are used to define the tasks in the workflow as well as the required runtime for them. As far as the HUTER project is concerned, the WDL format is the recommended.

If further information about Cromwell is required, please visit <https://cromwell.readthedocs.io/en/stable>.

4.4.1.2. Backend

Cromwell was developed for running on several deployment platforms and integrating with their services. Regarding HUTER Platform, Cromwell can run on the AWS infrastructure and easily communicate to the AWS S3 storage service. Furthermore, Cromwell provides a connector for managing the AWS Batch service that offers almost unlimited resources what breaks the limitation of personal computers, workstations and even on premises computing clusters.

However, for running a suitable environment on AWS it is required to previously define it as a docker container with the right software. Users can define their own docker containers and install on them the desired software for running their workflow. To do that, HUTER Platform provides repositories for saving the container definitions and the docker images.

For further information about the Cromwell integration with the backend on AWS, please visit <https://cromwell.readthedocs.io/en/stable/backends/AWSBatch>.

4.4.2. Repository

HUTER Platform offers a set of tools for saving required resources by Cromwell on AWS. These tools are known as repositories, and they are focus on two different resources:

- Code repository. It is a service that allows user to remotely save source code files. Besides, any change is stored so it is possible to keep track of any file modification. This repository is provided as a GITEA service using the well-known version control system, git. On this repository users can store their WDL and the dockerfile definitions for building the docker container that will be run on AWSBatch.
- Container repository. Once users have defined the required runtimes for their WDL using dockerfiles, HUTER Platforms automatically builds the container from those dockerfiles. The resulting docker images are stored in a docker Container Registry that is integrated with AWS Batch.

4.4.3. HUTER API - Processing

The HUTER API exposes a service that works as a facade for managing the executions requests under the HUTER Platform.

4.4.3.1. *huter-pipeline-manager-executions*

This service is responsible for integrating all the underlying services involved in the workflow execution and it is essential for a proper tracking of the processes in the platform. It exposes the API shown in *Figure 19 - huter-pipeline-manager-executions operations* for accepting the requests.

Regarding its aims, the *huter-pipeline-manager-executions* uses the *4.3.1 HUTER API – Data Access* for registering the execution of a workflow, its metadata and the location of their outcomes. It also works against the *Repository* for retrieving the workflow definition to be run.

Figure 19 - huter-pipeline-manager-executions operations

4.4.4. **HUTER CLI - Processing**

Deliverable *HUTER_WP7_D7.2_Visual_system_and_Digitalisation_software* introduced the user interaction with the HUTER CLI for requesting the execution of high throughput processes over stored files in the platform.

Figure 20 - huter-cli Cromwell

shows the command-line options that let users to provide the required data for the 4.4.3 HUTER API - Processing. So, no data processing is made on the user machine, just the communication against the HUTER Platform.

```

C:\Windows\System32\cmd.exe
D:\desenrola\huter\data-access-tools\huter-cli>java -jar huter-cli-dev-u.01.03.jar cromwell -h
huter-cli - 01.03.0000-SNAPSHOT - dev - Loading cromwell...
huter-cli - 01.03.0000-SNAPSHOT - dev - Running requested execution...
huter-cli - 01.03.0000-SNAPSHOT - dev -

This command requests the execution in the Cromwell infrastructure of a known pipeline. Pipeline has to exist on the platform code repository, Gitea.

Available cromwell options
-----

-p (mandatory)
  Folder name gitea repository that contains the WDL script describing the pipeline process.

-m (optional)
  Relative or absolute path to the manifest file containing the input files to be processed. Manifest file has to be updated by the user in order to assign the input variable name that expects the WDL script.

-u (optional)
  Relative or absolute path to a tsu file containing the key-value pairs with additional parameters needed for customizing the WDL script execution. Expected TSU columns:
  key | value
  -----
  simpleInputTestPipeline.intVariable | 1
  simpleInputTestPipeline.floatVariable | 2.55
  simpleInputTestPipeline.stringVariable | DownsamplingPowerOf2
  simpleInputTestPipeline.booleanVariable | true

-d (mandatory)
  Custom description of the process that runs over the provided files.

-u (mandatory)
  Unique identifier of the requested cromwell process to update its status based on cromwell pipeline status.
  NOTE: this option must be provided without any other options to correctly execute process update.

-h
  It shows this help.

huter-cli - 01.03.0000-SNAPSHOT - dev - The operation was successfully executed
D:\desenrola\huter\data-access-tools\huter-cli>
  
```

Figure 20 - huter-cli Cromwell

4.5. Others

HUTER Platform also provides some additional tools for increasing the user experience when they access to the data.

4.5.1. NextCloud

NextCloud constitutes a management data repository as well as a virtual office. It is devoted to facilitating the HUTER project managing work among partners located in different countries. For this purpose, NextCloud provides a useful suite of open-source tools, designed with a user-friendly interface for collaborative work, data sharing, videoconference, shared calendars and office tools.

The data and information gathered in this module are related to coordination tasks and documents repository instead of researching, albeit it is considered a data access tool for management roles.

This tool suffered from no modifications since it was introduced in deliverable *HUTER_WP2_D2.3_Beta_version_of_access_tools*.

4.5.2. Private user portal

HUTER Platform was designed as a heterogeneous environment where several applications can run independently but also integrated through services. This approach, backed by the AWS infrastructure, makes HUTER Platform a flexible environment that can easily deploy new tools for working with stored data. However, a continuous modification of the tool set could be annoying and confusing for users because they always should be up to date on the tool set.

The private portal is expected to be the guide page where users can see the list of HUTER tools they have permission to run.

5. ADVANCED DICOM VIEWER

Advanced DICOM Viewer is a solution for visualizing sample images stored in any of the DICOM formats proposed in deliverable *HUTER_WP2_D2.5_DICOM_implementation*. Those images are taken by digital microscopes from physical samples using experimental capture protocols and then, they are transformed into the proposed DICOM structures by BAHIA. The aim of this viewer is to provide a Proof-of-Concept tool to visualize these new imaging formats based on DICOM and offering a minimal set of advanced tools for imaging analysis in research assays through Artificial Intelligence over DICOM format.

The UI features for imaging visualization in the DICOM Viewer were introduced in deliverable *HUTER_WP7_D7.2_Visual_system_and_Digitalisation_software* so this section will go in depth with the architecture that supports its execution.

5.1. Supported imaging formats

This section will list the supported imaging files in DICOM format, their characteristics and how the viewer deal with them to display in a web application. Remember that the dicomization process explained in *HUTER_WP7_D7.2_Visual_system_and_Digitalisation_software* defines high-resolution images as pyramidal structures where each level is composed by small tiles as shown in *Figure 21 - DICOM pyramidal structure*.

Figure 21 - DICOM pyramidal structure

5.1.1. Immunohistochemistry

Brightfield microscopy is the traditionally preferred method of pathologists for diagnosing (e.g. widely used for diagnosis of cancers) using common staining techniques such as haematoxylin and eosin staining and immunohistochemistry (IHC).¹ IHC is a powerful microscopy-based technique for visualizing cellular components, for instance proteins or other macromolecules in tissue samples. Although it can be used with fluorescent markers attached to antibodies, IHC is typically performed using antibodies with chromogens in clinical environments. Chromogens are chemical compounds used in IHC labelling procedures that produce a coloured product that can be visualized by light microscopy. Thus, the tissue slides marked with these kinds of antibodies and the haematoxylin-eosin staining (which is a chemical and visible staining) can be analysed using traditional light microscopes. Therefore, the images can be acquired by digital scanners, like a common photography with high resolution. In this context, specific and expensive scanners and lasers are not required to excite and detect fluorophores like in advanced fluorescent microscopy.

The Advanced DICOM viewer has Immunohistochemistry image display capabilities and supports this type of study as well as haematoxylin and eosin images following the DICOM standard supplements 122 and 145, see *Figure 22 - Immunohistochemistry image in DICOM format.*

The functionalities allowed on these studies are the generic ones (navigation through the image, zoom, information display and so on) as well as AI algorithms, like segmentation and cell counting.

Figure 22 - Immunohistochemistry image in DICOM format

5.1.2. Tissue microarray

A Tissue Micro Array (TMA) image has the same base structure as Immunohistochemistry ones, but it also features multiple specimens within the same container. This feature together with the fact that DICOM standard for this kind of images was not fully developed and therefore implemented yet, becomes this type of image in an important challenge to be addressed in this project. In fact, there was not open DICOM viewers compatible with the Tissue Microarray image peculiarities developed until to date with diagnostic quality and advanced features. Part of the challenge is related with the development of the DICOM implementation which was not totally defined and implemented when the HUTER project started. We provide a DICOM evolution to overcome the implementation problems of TMA in our next deliverable D2.5.

Regarding the BAHIA proposal for the DICOM standard evolution, a set of objects called PRs are supported for locating and enriching each specimen data in the image as shown in *Figure 23 – Visualization of a Tissue Micro Array image in proposed DICOM format*.

Figure 23 – Visualization of a Tissue Micro Array image in proposed DICOM format

Tissue Micro Array images are visualized as any other *Immunohistochemistry* study in the Advanced DICOM Viewer. Once opened, we will see the images and the PRs objects displayed as red circles, but the border of said circle can be green if the PR is already assigned to a specimen (see Figure 24). To open the specimen list related to a study, the user must click in the icon marked by the black arrow at Figure 24. Once the list is opened, the user can assign specimens to a PR by dragging the PR over the specimen; the user can also unassign a PR by click the X icon on the PR Circle. If a specimen is already assigned to a PR, it will appear with a green background and it cannot be drag, the user must first unassign said specimen from its PR. This is relatively easy as the PRs are highlighted in blue when the user hovers over their assigned specimen.

Users can also adjust the size and location of the PRs manually for fitting the specimen shape by moving the circle symbolizing de PR. For this last purpose, users can also perform an automatic fitting process by clicking on the icon marked by the yellow arrow at Figure 24. The image study is then processed by a Computer Vision algorithm that locates the specimens on the image and estimates their radius. The user can make then the adjustments that he/she considers appropriate. This algorithm is very helpful, a manually annotation of the PRs (object that represents title, description, location, and radius) can take 5s/PR, with 100 prs is almost 10 minutes. With this automatically location algorithm, the location of PRs is way faster. The automatic location algorithm is a Python service that finds circular samples on a given TMA image that uses the following techniques: KMeans with k= 2 to obtain two main colours. We threshold the image based on those 2 colours. The whitest is taken as background and the rest as foreground. Finally, we detect the contours of each specimen and estimate the centre and radius of it as the half mean of height and width (radius) of the bounding box (smaller box that contains a specimen) and its centre, respectively.

Once the PRs are correctly located, the user needs to indicate which PR corresponds to which specimen on the list. We can do it dragging the item on the list and dropping it on the corresponding circle. To save the modifications, we simply click on the “Save” button in the right panel marked by the red arrow. The user can show or hide the PRs by toggling the eye button in the right panel marked by the green arrow.

5.1.3. Immunofluorescence

Immunofluorescence is a method in biology that relies on the use of antibodies chemically labelled with a fluorophore to visualize molecules using specialized fluorescence microscopes with filters (typically for red, yellow and blue wavelengths) along with specific laser emitters to visualize the antibodies. This technique uses the specificity of an antibody with its antigen to label a specific target in a biological sample, such as cells or tissues. Unlike the traditional immunohistochemistry that is based on chromogens, the antibodies of immunofluorescence techniques have a fluorophore (directly or indirectly) attached to them and thus allow visualization of the distribution of the labelled targets in the sample by stimulating the fluorophores (with distinct emission spectra) with specific wavelengths.

Another important point of immunofluorescence is that it allows to identify more than three markers in the same sample section at the same time. This means that the clinicians and researchers can get more information in the same experiment. This technique is called multiplexed immunofluorescence. Despite clinical immunohistochemistry has been predominantly brightfield-based, multiplexing is typically performed using immunofluorescence since multiplexing in brightfield has been problematic for two main reasons: a) small number of chromogens which limits the marker combinations and b) brightfield microscopy cameras only detect three defined colours.¹ Common chromogens, typically used in Immunohistochemistry, have absorbance peaks with full width at half maxima of 200 nm or more (e.g., 3,3'-diaminobenzidine and Fast Red) compared with fluorophores with full width at half maxima typically between 30 and 60 nm in solution.² This means that two or three chromogens in combination may fill the entire visible spectrum, with considerable spectral overlap between chromogens. In this scenario, immunofluorescence allows to combine more fluorescent antibodies and therefore obtain multiplexed images with more information than immunohistochemistry ones. Immunofluorescence microscopy can detect multiple fluorescent antibodies with different emission spectrum in a single sample section, therefore multiple antigens can be detected through the detection of different emission wavelength of each antibody. In this context, the Advanced DICOM viewer allows to see these images, including different fluorescent markers, from a DICOM image which could

¹ Morrison, L. E., Lefever, M. R., Behman, L. J., Leibold, T., Roberts, E. A., Horchner, U. B., & Bauer, D. R. (2020). Brightfield multiplex immunohistochemistry with multispectral imaging. *Laboratory Investigation*, 100(8), 1124-1136.

² Day, W. A., Lefever, M. R., Ochs, R. L., Pedata, A., Behman, L. J., Ashworth-Sharpe, J., ... & Morrison, L. E. (2017). Covalently deposited dyes: a new chromogen paradigm that facilitates analysis of multiple biomarkers in situ. *Laboratory Investigation*, 97(1), 104-113.

foster the implementation of this images in clinical environments due to the interoperability advantages of this format.

In the DICOM viewer, immunofluorescence images can show different visualizations from same view changing the antibody applied, because of that, there is multiple channels for sample, one for each fluorescent dye as shown in *Figure 24 – Visualization of immunofluorescence image in proposed DICOM format*. For each antigen, the proposed DICOM structure stores its information in a different pyramidal structure, therefore the Advanced DICOM Viewer has to manage a DICOM pyramidal structure for each channel image.

The viewer allows all functions from Immunohistochemistry and add a new feature to manage the channels and to filter the intensity of the fluorescence levels with the aim of visualize the regions with more (or less) levels of antigen.

Figure 24 – Visualization of immunofluorescence image in proposed DICOM format

5.1.4. smFISH

Single molecule fluorescence *in situ* hybridization (smFISH) is a powerful technique to study gene expression due to its ability to detect RNA molecules in biological sections. Complementary to deep sequencing-based methods, smFISH provides information about the cell-to-cell variation in transcript abundance and the subcellular localization of a given RNA.³ The smFISH technique is based on the use of oligonucleotide probes to target different regions of the same mRNA transcript. The transcripts and probes suffer a hybridization

³ Battich, N., Stoeger, T., & Pelkmans, L. (2013). Image-based transcriptomics in thousands of single human cells at single-molecule resolution. *Nature methods*, 10(11), 1127-1133.

process. Because each oligo is conjugated with only one fluorophore, it is faintly visible by itself. Binding of multiple oligos to the same transcript yields a bright spot, indicative of a single mRNA transcript.

The Advanced DICOM viewer was designed to be compatible with the smFISH images in the BAHIA’s standard evolution of DICOM format as shown in *Figure 25 – Visualization of a smFISH image in proposed DICOM format*.

Regarding to the smFISH imaging structure, it contains information of several wavelength channels like *Immunofluorescence* ones but also, for each point, it offers several layers obtained by applying different lent focus. In terms of DICOM imaging structure, it means that the Advanced DICOM Viewer has to manage a different pyramidal structure for each channel and z-axis image in the original image which is one of the main innovation challenges of this type of image.

Figure 25 – Visualization of a smFISH image in proposed DICOM format

The visualization of smFISH studies offers all *Immunofluorescence* imaging functionalities for navigating and zooming through the image channels. Furthermore, the Advanced DICOM Viewer also provides a new feature to navigate across z-axis of each channel in the image. Therefore, this tool offers a free navigation through all the graphical information stored in the smFISH images.

5.2. Artificial Intelligence applied to research images

Artificial Intelligence is an existing tool that in the recent days has become the very latest fashion for supporting data analysis. Regarding to imaging analysis, AI can be applied to different uses cases: human error reduction in specimen handling and processing, faster turnaround times, workload management, quality

control and quality assurance measures, automatic requests of relevant tests in certain cases and automatic reporting.

Although there are several subareas in the Artificial Intelligence discipline, the most interesting in this context is the Artificial Vision and how to apply it over DICOM images. In the context of the HUTER project we explored the potential of AI to improve the categorization of imaging areas applying previously trained algorithms so users could have a previous map of the image. At the same time, we also explored how AI can contribute to the identification of unhealthy/healthy entities and with the quantification of the number of diagnostic components which may be important to promote the use of AI algorithms in routine clinical practice.

Despite the race by research groups and industry to produce and license AI based technologies, it should be noted that few solutions have achieved reliable clinical utility of and produced the desired impact. There are several reasons behind the low adoption of AI products in real clinical practice and particularly to imaging solutions. Some of the solutions are very much focused on the analytical performance and they are not good enough to provide enough clinical utility. In other words, the developed AI algorithms do not consider important aspects for clinicians like the costs, risks and value added for the patient and the user when they are compared with the existing practice. Additionally, clinicians use certain evidence-based clinical data to make a diagnosis, it is expected that image-based AI tools would use the same well-defined clinical data and volumes to reach the same level of confidence in making a diagnosis as pathologists do. The concept of volume is critical, because for this development we will need high-quality data to achieve reliable results.

In the context of the HUTER project we have been evaluating several algorithms and models and we finally have chosen the Ilastik tool⁴ for the Advanced DICOM Viewer. Researchers from various application domains have successfully used Ilastik in their work⁵ to segment, classify, track and count cells or other experimental data, so we propose the use of Ilastik to the images generated by HUTER. The most challenging issues to tackle with by the visualization tool was the integration of Ilastik with the proposed DICOM formats and the availability of enough data in the HUTER repositories to train the algorithms.

5.2.1. Ilastik

As introduced before, Ilastik is an interactive learning and segmentation toolkit that allows the generation of algorithms of computer vision easily with an UI, recently reported in *Nature Methods*.⁶ The toolkit is based on the computation of low-level features as colour, edges, and textures, and then it applies a machine learning

⁴ <https://www.ilastik.org/>

⁵ Li, C., Ma, X., Deng, J., Li, J., et al. Machine learning-based automated fungal cell counting under a complicated background with ilastik and ImageJ. *Eng Life Sci.* 2021; 21: 769– 777. <https://doi.org/10.1002/elsc.202100055>

⁶ Berg, S., Kutra, D., Kroeger, T. et al. ilastik: interactive machine learning for (bio)image analysis. *Nat Methods* 16, 1226–1232 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-019-0582-9>

method, as Random Forest to classify/segment the image. Other techniques as CNN and U-Nets can be used also for classification, segmentation, and cell-counting. However, with this toolkit is more simple and easier to edit and create new algorithms without too much data, without full-supervision and with a useful UI.

Ilastik provides a toolkit for manually training the segmentation and counting algorithms over a set of images as shown in *Figure 26 - Ilastik Toolkit. Segmentation algorithm training.*

Figure 26 - Ilastik Toolkit. Segmentation algorithm training.

Once algorithm is trained, it can be applied to DICOM images from a background process. On the backend program that periodically queries all studies in PACS and then checks for the segmentation status in the database. The backend downloads the level of the pyramid with the best resolution and segments it with Ilastik. Once the segmentation images are generated, the remaining levels of the pyramid are generated using the segmented images by subsampling in Java and stored in a directory structure in the backend, with one folder per segmentation type and inside, one per level. When the user opens the study, he/she can enable segmentation layers that shows the segmentation images mixed with the original image (with an alpha). The frontend requests a segmented image by study, segmentation type, level and coordinates, and the backend returns the image of the pyramid directory.

5.2.2. Segmentation/Clustering

Semantic segmentation is very helpful tool for supporting the visualization of high-resolution images. Segmentation or clustering is an Artificial Intelligence technique that chases the categorization of each area in an image using a previous trained algorithm.

Figure 27 - Original image for segmentation

For HUTER project, an algorithm was trained for segmentation on immunohistochemistry images like the one shown in *Figure 27 - Original image for segmentation*.

Using that image as input for the already segmentation algorithm, the segmentation ends up in a new image where the palette of colours categorizes of region the image. *Figure 28 - Example of segmentation image* shows the result of the segmentation of the algorithm that was trained for recognizing the existing cells in the image. Green areas mean those where cells are expected to be located, whereas pink ones show the areas where cells are not identified.

After a human analysis, we confirmed the segmentation capabilities of the AI algorithm through the identification of the container border and anchoring points as cells. Besides, the trained AI algorithm also properly detected areas in the body sample as represented in *Figure 28*.

However, in the sample body many points are rightly detected as cells, so we will need further research to attain a higher accuracy levels. The inaccuracy of this results could be due to the small training dataset because no container border or anchor images were analysed during the learning process.

Figure 28 - Example of segmentation

Ilastik can be also applied to the other images generated by HUTER researchers, like Immunofluorescence or smFISH. These images are not brightfield images because their markers require specific wavelengths to excite their fluorophores in order to detect the emission wavelengths. That is why both image types offer a set of channels related to the wavelength detected after exciting the fluorophores.

The previously trained algorithm can be trained for the segmentation of a multichannel fluorescent-based image like smFISH shown in *Figure 29 - smFISH image for segmentation test*.

Figure 29 - smFISH image for segmentation test

As far as we know this is the first application of the model algorithm to multichannel fluorescent-based images in DICOM. The result of applying the segmentation algorithm over the smFISH image is shown in *Figure 30 - Segmentation algorithm over smFISH image*. Herein, the algorithm was not able to accurately identify the information on the image. This reveals that the algorithm training was not appropriate for properly applying segmentation on fluorescence images. As a consequence, we will need to initiate a new R&D strategy developing new mathematical models for multichannel-fluorescent based images.⁷

The result of the R&D done so far is that though, Ilastik is a useful tool that offers the capacity for training algorithms which are able to segmentate images, it lacks enough performance to address the challenges of smFISH images. In order to obtain a better performance, we need to initiate a more ambitious R&D project with access to a higher number of smFISH images. In other words, to obtain a good segmentation performance of smFISH images, we will need an adequate algorithm training phase and this is only achievable with a meaningful set of sample frames. Besides, a correct identification of the image characteristics that provides the most remarkable values for area categorization is also essential for the algorithm training process. Hence, the training phase should be also done with a significant number of manually labelled smFISH images. For instance, on fluorescence images like smFISH, channel features should be considered during the algorithm training process. Unfortunately, in the context of the HUTER project researchers have only produced a limited number of smFISH images which also limited the capacity to develop, train and test new mathematical models for multichannel fluorescence-based images like smFISH. A new research line for the development of a new algorithm could be opened in the future if more smFISH images are finally available through the HUTER platform or the Human Cell Atlas Platform.

⁷ A) Meijering, Erik. (2020). A Bird's-Eye View of Deep Learning in Bioimage Analysis. Computational and Structural Biotechnology Journal. 18. 10.1016/j.csbj.2020.08.003. B) Suzuki, G., Saito, Y., Seki, M. et al. Machine learning approach for discrimination of genotypes based on bright-field cellular images. npj Syst Biol Appl 7, 31 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41540-021-00190-w>

Figure 30 - Segmentation algorithm over smFISH image

Even though, Ilastik is a useful tool that offers the capacity for training algorithms which are able to segmentate images. The key point resides in a correct algorithm training that can be achieved by providing a meaningful set of sample frames. Besides, a correct identification of the image characteristics that provides the most remarkable values for area categorization is essential for the algorithm learning process. For instance, on fluorescence images like smFISH, channel features should be considered during the algorithm training process.

5.2.3. Cellular counting

Cell density is also an important factor used by clinicians and scientists to evaluate a sample, quantifying the differences between tumour and benign regions of tissue and consequently to determine the progression of the disease. Manually counting cells is a tedious task that consumes a lot of time. HUTER Viewer explored the use of machine learning based density Ilastik counting algorithm to automatically count the number of cells on a given image. In order to perform the counting, the user should select an area, this area can be a rectangle or a free form polygon. The coordinates of that area with respect to the level is sent to the backend where the program has to build an image by joining the tiles of the level with the highest resolution. Then, the process crops the resulting image to the required area. Once the image is created, it is processed by Ilastik-based algorithm, which counts the number of cells. Once counted, the number of cells and the density is plotted on the screen, reducing the amount of time required to count each cell manually to just the time needed to indicate the area where we want to count cells.

The flow for this functionality is the following. First the user selects the desired tool to count, the free form polygon tool (marked by the green arrow at *Figure 31 - Counting tool from DICOM Advanced Viewer interface*).

To finish the marking in the first tool, the user must click on the X of the first point, while for the later the user must click on the tick icon inside the rectangle.

Figure 31 - Counting tool from DICOM Advanced Viewer interface

After the server processes the counting results, it returns three different objects: the number of cells, the processed image, and the base image. All this information is blended in a new modal, in which the user can select the desired opacity of the processed shown in Figure 32 - Resulting image of counting algorithm.

Figure 32 - Resulting image of counting algorithm

For applying cell counting algorithm, there are three different possibilities: if the study is as immunochemistry or TMA one, then the count request is sent to the server because there is only one layer of images. However, for smFISH studies the request of cell counting is also sent to the server because have several channels depending on the number of fluorescent channels (see Figure 33 - smFISH counting selection). The DAPI staining, which is commonly used to mark cell nucleus enabling cell counting (typically one nucleus, one cell), is already defined in the native image file of smFISH.

Figure 33 - smFISH counting selection

However, in the case of immunofluorescence images the user must first select the desired channel for counting due to the lack of this information in the native image (before DICOM transformation), as shown in Figure 34 – Immunofluorescence channel selection for counting.

Figure 34 – Immunofluorescence channel selection for counting

The result of the counting process of an smFISH image is shown in Figure 35 - smFISH counting result. Ilastik-based algorithms were used to process the section marked in order to detect nucleus and count. Although the algorithm provides a good performance in immunohistochemistry and TMA images, its performance in smFISH and Immunofluorescence was not as good as the immunohistochemistry and TMA. The algorithm was not able

to accurately count the cells based on the DAPI channel. This reveals that the algorithm training was not appropriate. Another important point is the number of the smFISH required to train the algorithm. It should be further increased to improve the accuracy of the cell counting. As previously commented for segmentation algorithms, a new specific research line could be opened to develop new algorithms for cell counting in complex images such as multiplexed immunofluorescence or smFISH in DICOM format.

However, taking into account the results over Immunohistochemistry images, Ilastik can offer a good feature for applying AI counting tools from the Advanced DICOM Viewer. Although a more expert training should be performed for generating a set of algorithms specialised on each imaging type.

Figure 35 - smFISH counting result

5.3. Platform integration

As part of the HUTER Platform toll suite, the Advanced DICOM Viewer is integrated with the deployed services and tools.

5.3.1. Security

This tool is integrated with the *Security* system deployed on the platform as any other tool, so the Single Sign On feature is applied when accessing it from the *Private user portal*.

5.3.2. PACS

The PACS is the solution to storage the DICOM images as well as providing a service facade for accessing images. Although the deployed PACS offers several DICOM standard interfaces, the Advanced DICOM Viewer integration is made through **REST** services, defined in the DICOMweb part of the DICOM Standard. Different

types of endpoints are used for different purposes: QIDO-RS to query studies and patient’s data, WADO-URI and WADO-RS to retrieve DICOM objects info, STOW-RS to store PRs and annotations.

Through these services can be obtained data such as:

- Information about study
- Information about patient
- Images of study
- Annotations made in study
- Information on the DICOM elements contained in PACS such as series and instances.

For the storage in PACS of annotations and regions of interest that viewer’s user has created, will be used STOW RS storage web services, which will communicate through the same HTTP and HTTPS protocols.

5.4. Architecture and technical design

This section will cover the technical design and requirements for running the Advanced DICOM Viewer on the HUTER Platform.

5.4.1. Component model

The diagram showed in *Figure 36 - Deployable components of the Advanced DICOM Viewer* represents the modular decomposition of the application, where the architecture and components used in the design of the proposed system can be identified and in which the different logical levels can be observed.

Figure 36 - Deployable components of the Advanced DICOM Viewer

Figure 36 - Deployable components of the Advanced DICOM Viewer shows the required components for running a full version of the Advanced DICOM Viewer. Components are the next:

- **PostgreSQL:** Internal database for user configuration and temporal data storage.

- **Amazon EFS Share:** Internal and temporary space for managing files employed by core.
- **Backend Core:** Tomcat server which get data from PACS, DB and Amazon EFS Share and offers it to Browser app.
- **Python Flask Server:** Server for some vectorial and computer vision operations.
- **Ilastik:** binaries for computer visions algorithms.
- **Browser app:** Display the Backend core functionalities to user. It is accessed externally with HTTPS protocol.
- **Keycloak:** Authentication system to manager platform users.
- **PACS:** Backend core uses DICOM and DICOM WADO standard to send and receive imaging data from it.

5.4.2. Development technologies

For the Advanced DICOM Viewer development, web development languages and environments intended will be used. The main technologies used to build the viewer will be AngularJS, Java, Spring and PostgreSQL. Obtained application will be deployed on a Tomcat server.

In addition to this, to achieve a responsive application, style libraries such as Bootstrap and technologies such as SASS will be used.

Server will have an exclusive storage area for user images, and it runs an asynchronous process for image upload and conversion system.

6. REFERENCES

1. Morrison, L. E., Lefever, M. R., Behman, L. J., Leibold, T., Roberts, E. A., Horchner, U. B., & Bauer, D. R. (2020). Brightfield multiplex immunohistochemistry with multispectral imaging. *Laboratory Investigation*, 100(8), 1124-1136.
2. Day, W. A., Lefever, M. R., Ochs, R. L., Pedata, A., Behman, L. J., Ashworth-Sharpe, J., ... & Morrison, L. E. (2017). Covalently deposited dyes: a new chromogen paradigm that facilitates analysis of multiple biomarkers in situ. *Laboratory Investigation*, 97(1), 104-113.
3. Battich, N., Stoeger, T., & Pelkmans, L. (2013). Image-based transcriptomics in thousands of single human cells at single-molecule resolution. *Nature methods*, 10(11), 1127-1133.
4. <https://www.ilastik.org/>
5. Li, C., Ma, X., Deng, J., Li, J., et al. Machine learning-based automated fungal cell counting under a complicated background with ilastik and ImageJ. *Eng Life Sci.* 2021; 21: 769– 777. <https://doi.org/10.1002/elsc.202100055>

6. Berg, S., Kutra, D., Kroeger, T. et al. ilastik: interactive machine learning for (bio)image analysis. *Nat Methods* 16, 1226–1232 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-019-0582-9>
7. A) Meijering, Erik. (2020). A Bird’s-Eye View of Deep Learning in Bioimage Analysis. *Computational and Structural Biotechnology Journal*. 18. 10.1016/j.csbj.2020.08.003. B) Suzuki, G., Saito, Y., Seki, M. et al. Machine learning approach for discrimination of genotypes based on bright-field cellular images. *npj Syst Biol Appl* 7, 31 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41540-021-00190-w>